

Traversing through the Night: Nocturnal Carnavalesque in Ahmed Ali's *Ocean of Night* and *A Night of Winter Rains*

Paper Id : 20632 Submission Date : 2025-07-07 Acceptance Date : 2025-07-22 Publication Date : 2025-07-25

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.17190278

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Abstract

The shift towards the 'night' in the modern world is no less of a revolution. Moving away from the stereotypical comprehension of the night-time as infested by spirits and necromancers. The turn towards the night changed human perceptions of the basic activities such as work, entertainment and primordially the idea of sleep. With intense 'colonization' of the night, human civilizations attained new means of both personal and spiritual enlightenment which served as new modes of interaction with the public sphere. The inherent duality of day and night, and the emphasis of the night has found its way to literature of various age. Though the ubiquity and ambiguity of the night make 'night' impossible for the literary critic to pin down in a uni-planer criticism, it provides an exceptional vantage point for the literary practitioners to draw from its potential to explore the space through an inverted point of view, both in terms of characterization and narration. This article shall deal with the aspects of nocturnalization as explored by Ahmed Ali (1910-1994) within the selected texts.

Keywords

Night, Nocturnal Carnavalesque, Ahmed Ali, Hierarchy, Night Space.

Introduction

"What is the night?" (III.IV.126)

Macbeth, W. Shakespeare

Night imposed fundamental limits on the human civilization, as well as providing evocative imageries which are explored in literatures of various periods. The most common attribution to the night before the modern era was that of the connotations of negative elements such as dark magic and ghosts, spirits and necromancers etc. Shakespeare explores this aspect in his play *Macbeth* (1623) in Act 3, Scene IV; after a disturbing encounter with Banquo's ghost, Macbeth poses the question to Lady Macbeth which is used as the epigraph to this article. When put under critical lens, the question both rises to a level of enquiry which gives us the sense of temporality as well as a sense of a rhetorical understanding of the 'night', which brings in various significations of the term within contexts of spatial, social as well as psychological space.

Symbolic attributions to nocturnal activities are fundamental to every culture. From ranges to theology to the studies of astrophysics, the night carries with it both positive and negative connotations. Society depends upon such attributions to assert and derive social meanings based upon perceptions of darkness within socio-cultural contexts. The exploration of the interplay between light and darkness can be traced back to ancient Greece, but its formal appearance evolved much later in the Italian Renaissance art of the 15th Century, the chiaroscuro (meaning 'light-dark'). The interplay of light and darkness provided unique perspectives and reshaped the way in which the world understood attributions of darkness (or light) in human world. In the late 16th Century, another Italian painter Michelangelo Caravaggio introduced tenebrism, an extreme form of contrast between light and darkness, depending upon the use of shadows to derive meaning to art. In literature though, the aspect of darkness is most poignantly elaborated by the phrase 'darkness visible' by John Milton in his *Paradise Lost* (1667); an oxymoron used by Milton to describe the Pandemonium, capital of Hell designed by the fallen angel Mulciber. This oxymoron along with the Pandemonium becomes synonymous with a state of absolute darkness, both literally as well as rhetorically which allows for both spiritual as well as physical darkness to be perceived. Around the same time, "the swift rise of public street lighting is the most salient: in 1660, no European city had permanently illuminated its streets, but by 1700 consistent and reliable street lighting had been established in Amsterdam, Pasis, Turin, London ..." (Koslofsky 2). The socio-cultural aspects attributed to the night (as *darkness*) has shifted dramatically after the advent of the modern age, it saw countless ways in which human society and culture have inhibited the night. The idea of an existence of a flipped perception which acts as an inherent psycho-social force is expressed as Carnavalesque by Mikhail Bakhtin, developed through his *Problems of Dostoyevsky's Poetics* (1929) and subsequently developed in "Rabelais and His World" (1965). Literature makes use of this idea extensively to present a reversal of psycho-social order within narration. One of the popular examples of contemporary times is the novel *Carnavalesque* (2017) by Neil Jordan. The author explores two personalities of the

protagonist Andy's (and Dany's) contrasting characteristics. The persona that is left behind in the carnival is called Andy and the one that goes back is called Dany. This is one of the many significant ways which the novel explores to dive deep into contrasting psychological behavior and social functions of various elements within the novel.

Ahmed Ali (1910-1994), a novelist, critic, poet and diplomat was born in Delhi (British India) is a prominent member of All India Progressive Writers' Association (AIPWA) who contributed to the *Angarey* (1932) considered as the inception of Progressive Writers' Movement in India. Ali's short story "A Night of Winter Rains" is a part of this collection. His second novel *Ocean of Night* (1964) can be considered a pen picture of the modern Indian developing cities. Through his literary creations, Ali explored the life and times of the people rooted in social realism as Premchand suggested, "It needs to be proven to us that what the writer created was created based on real experiences and that he himself is speaking from his character's tongues." (78). To do so Ali extensively uses the literary space or the narrated space as his medium to convey deep messages about the social conditions, human agency and his character's psychology. Despite a deeply rooted geographical realism as a formal technique, Ali makes use of the geography to tell his tale so much so that the place itself appears as a character in the novel, reacting to the plot in various ways.

Objective of study

It is widely considered that Ahmed Ali's fiction is deeply rooted in geographic realism, which in turn contributes to the aesthetic purpose of his attributed characterization to the places narrated within his fiction. But it is also interesting to note that his fiction despite being rooted in geographic realism, inherently makes use of temporal consciousness of the nighttime, both as a metaphor and a means to convey deeper meanings within the discourse of his fiction. This paper shall try to focus on the nocturnal elements in Ahmed Ali's selected texts, namely *Ocean of Night* (1964) and "A Night of Winter Rains" (1932).

Review of Literature

George Rhäticus's *Narratio prima* (1540-41) has been one of the instrumental texts in understanding the night because of rotation of the Earth, he was a student of Copernicus who studied the rotations of the celestial bodies and contributed to our primary understandings of astronomy. The darkness of space was a matter of ignorance till the medieval times, which was considered as a mere shadow of the Earth's conical hemisphere. In his other work, Criag Kosofsky in his *Evening's Empire* (2011) who has contextualized the perception of night in the early modern times within three important aspects: sleep, site for every quotidian activity, a symbol of great force in popular and learned culture. Gerrit Verhoeven in his article "The Remains of the Night" (2023) explored how the advent of street lighting impacted popular behaviour; demonstrating the aspects of inhibition of the 'night' by human interventions giving shape to new social orders. In his thesis submitted to the University of North Carolina titled "The Night Unraveled: Nocturnal Significances in Seventeenth-Century French Court Ballets" (2024), Matteo Sammartano explored the 'night' as a "potent vehicle" to forward political messages within a "spectacular framework". It explores one of the most essential aspects of nocturnalization in creating political spectacles by "amalgamating music, dance, poetry [using] political undertones" in French courtrooms. Exploring both the idea of carnivalesque, as well as its use as a subaltern tool – focusing on darkness as an essential tool to overcome nominal inferiorities. In her Doctoral Thesis titled "Venice Nightscapes: Consuming, Living, Narrating" (2025), Giuseppe Tomasella explored how nightscapes co-produces "ongoing, fleeting and reciprocal relations between bodies, objects, places and discourses" which in turn has a lasting and prominent effect over "economy, nocturnal social practices and night-themed narratives". These scholars and their contributions have contextualized nocturnal activities in terms of necessity and leisure, order and disorder. It is primarily from these aspects of the nocturnalization which this paper draws its framework from.

Main Text

Faces of the Night: Tracing Nocturnal Negotiations

The 'night' has been central to our understandings of binaries, literatures make extensive use of symbols, metaphors, imageries and various connotations associated with it. Ahmed Ali in his novel *Ocean of Night* (1964) makes extensive use of 'night', both to derive rhetorical meaning from it as well as to set his narrative geography. The novel's subtitle, 'A haunting, romantic tale of a Lucknow courtesan' itself raises the first level of metaphor that the title employs. The title and the subtitle together try to establish a route of signification whereby 'night' is associated with the haunting and the psychosis of fear. The novel opens with an epigraph from "A Lucknow Poet":

"May Lucknow last beyond all harm,

It still is better than many a place..." (Ali 5)

The epigraph takes us to the immediate setting of the novel, that is Lucknow. Ali employs the aestheticism of the lyric epigraph to forward the idea of the place (the geography), then immediately moves on to talk about the temporal essence of his setting as:

"Night, like the heart of lover, conceals within it the mystery of life. Shut between the common world of days, it hides the secrets of human passion. Hatred and jealousy, love

and frustration are known to it as the moods of the loved one are to the lovers.” (Ali 5).

Being the first line of the novel, it evokes the temporal essence of ‘night’ and what it conceals within; Ali skillfully stages the geography of the night in relation to all its connotations and all its ambivalences. The social attributions that Ali assign to the nightscape serve as a reminder of the inherent contrasts within the human characters and their psycho-social behaviour during the ‘night’.

Ahmed Ali’s short story “A Night of Winter Rains” paints a different picture of the ‘night’, harsh and unforgiving environment, and within it the struggles of the human condition. The story presents the fear or the psychosis of dark, beginning with:

“*Garr! Garr! Garr!* It seems the sky will rip open. The roof’s not coming down, it is? ... *Whiissh, whiissh!* How cold it is! Freezing, icy. This shivering rattles every bone in my body.” (Ali, “A Night of Winter Rains” 195).

The human world encounters nature’s vicious and relentless furies, the ‘night’ further exaggerates the hardships of the human condition. An elevated sense of fear is expressed within this story which is combined with a sense of darkness and the nature’s furies upon the human condition which the narrator claims, “Like a newborn kitten, I have peeked into every nook and corner, but there’s no peace anywhere.” (Ali, “A Night of Winter Rains” 195). The condition presented here is rooted in its deep affliction of the human mind with fear – Ali skillfully combines that internal fear with the external conditions such as rain and darkness of the night, which produces such combined effects in the narrative.

The doleful forgetfulness of the turmoil of the human condition is accompanied by the darkness of the night. The fear of the unknown itself harbours within it the forgetfulness of the miseries of existence. Ahmed Ali employs this technique to present a condition of momentary relief that the night carries:

“But Night, the captivating *saqi*, brings out its glittering cups and, drunk and the breeze that makes them dream and forget, they care not for the intruders into their lives. Dancing they go through the courtyards of life, dancing they pass into the halls of death.” (Ali 5).

Ali emphasizes upon the momentary respite that the night offers, the indulgence that blurs the thin boundary of the centrality of binary oppositions within the human condition. Within a cultural context:

“the ‘True’ is always marked and informed by the ambivalence of the process of emergence itself, the productivity of meanings that construct counter-knowledges in *medias res*, in the very act of agonism, within the terms of negotiation (rather than a negation) of oppositional and antagonistic elements.” (Bhaba 22).

What Homi K. Bhaba expressed as the simultaneous presence of opposing consciousness in *medias res* is explored by Ahmed Ali as the consciousness of opposing forces that guide the human consciousness through the encounter of darkness (and night). The considerable importance given to the atmosphere which enables the night a space which blurs the boundaries of the center and the periphery, where opposing forces co-exist and produce a liminal space whereby opposing perceptions mingle to develop an ambivalent condition. This ambivalence is later manifested.

Shapes of the Night: Looking through Nocturnal Narration

The daily rhythm of social life is stopped at the advent of night, the night serves as a boundary between what is perceived as socially appropriate code of conducts and what the society sanctioned. What is considered essential is thus put unto the question, did nocturnalization radically unhinge the everyday rhythm of the society in terms of work, leisure, entertainment as well as sleep? What Mikhail M. Bakhtin argued in his work “Rabelais and His World” is that:

“As opposed to the official feast, one might say that carnival celebrated temporary liberation from the prevailing truth and from the established order; it marked the suspension of all hierarchical rank, privileges, norms, and prohibitions.” (Rivkin and Ryan 686).

This contrast of suspension of established order between the day and the night is explored by Ahmed Ali within the selected texts. *Ocean of Night* explores the aspect of reversal of roles in a poignant way; let us consider an episode from the novel where Murad Ali (a character, the servant of Nawab Chakkan in the novel) is asked to deliver a message to Huma (the society courtesan) by his master who along with Namdar Hassan (another servant) sets on the errand. During their journey, the conversation between the two takes place in the following manner:

‘It has to do with me that we cannot forget the errand we are going on.’ (Namdar Hassan)

'And if we forget?' (Murad Ali)

'And if we forget, you fool, we shall lose our jobs.' (Namdar Hassan)

'Lose our jobs' the other said mockingly. 'Who will dismiss us? The Nawab?
He will not.' (Murad Ali) " (Ali 7).

The conversation between the two servants carries an inherent sense of rebellion, a protest within. The indication of subversion of the established hierarchy, the inversion of their expected social behaviour is an essence nocturnal carnivalesque. The night reveals a state where the established social order is suspended, the distinct boundary of the center (the authority of Nawab Chakkan) and the periphery (servants Murad Ali and Namdar Hassan) blurred with the advent of night.

Night affects the social hierarchies, boundary within the social strata dissipates and there is a collective unconsciousness that prevails in the space (as in atmosphere). This aspect is promptly observed in the case of entertainment (or 'feast' as proposed by Bakhtin) that take place in the night. Ali uses this specific metaphor to promote a social condition where an active sense of collective can be observed among the characters where the archetype is the struggle for authority. Indulgence of hedonistic entertainment provides a momentary relapse which is explored as a 'feast':

'Bring the cups and the bottle.' Nawab Chakkan ordered.

'You will excuse me, *huzoor*,' Murad Ali begged. 'This daughter of the grape (a form of wine) is too much for me.'

'Not only you will drink,' said the Nawab resolutely, 'but you will dance as well until Huma (the courtesan) comes here.'

And the drinking continued late into the hours of the night, until they lost consciousness of their particular worries and fell asleep under the influence of this intermediary between sleep and waking, life and death." (Ali 14)

Manifestation of a collective unconsciousness is seen in the form of entertainment, Nawab Chakkan ordered Murad Ali to 'dance' but indulged in drinking, Murad Ali refused to drink but could adhere to his decision. The entertainment descended into a state of relapse, the night brought a sense of sterility making the social hierarchy ineffective filled with indolence and leisure.

Conclusion

Normative 'Night' Space

Ahmed Ali through his fiction makes use of the metaphors of 'night' to forward his symbolic messages. The idea of an inherent carnivalesque is associated with 'night' (or darkness) within the social context. This aspect has been explored through the aspects of manifestation of the physical space within narratives of the selected texts. The psychological space of the characters, their sense of collective unconsciousness, the fear or psychosis of the dark and a native sense of rebellion and protest which has been observed within the selected texts of Ahmed Ali promotes the aspect of nocturnal carnivalesque. A reversal of the normative social order which is seen at the advent of 'night', which is a major marker of the sense of the connotation of nocturnal spaces that harbours within it a sense of ambivalent existence which is one of the major highlights of a narrated 'night' space.

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